

Mind-body interventions for highly sensitive persons: a mixed-method systematic review. Review protocol.

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Introduction

A growing body of evidence supports the impact of personality on exercise participation. Sensory processing sensitivity (SPS) is a temperamental trait characterized by increased awareness and sensitivity to the environment. Highly sensitive persons (HSPs) process environmental, social, and emotional stimuli and information more deeply than usual (Boterberg & Warreyn, 2016) and this includes sensitivity to pain, overstimulation, strong sensory input, over-aroused by external stimuli and being observed by others, which has practical implications for exercise promotion. SPS is a relevant predictor of stress, psychological distress (mental disorders as well as emotional and somatic symptoms), and occupational burnout, also in healthy individuals (van den Boogert et al., 2022).

Mind-body therapies typically use a holistic approach that targets the individual as a whole rather than a particular need or ability (Simmons-Mackie & Damico, 2007). Holistic approaches promote person-centered care and self-regulation strategies, and they may be a useful tool for empowering people with high SPS levels to become more adept at managing their emotional circumstances in daily life (De Silva, 2011).

Mind-body approaches can be considered holistic and person-centred approaches, focusing on behavioural exercises, mindful movement or somatic education to promote mind-body connection and well-being. These usually group-based approaches impart self-regulation strategies and might empower individuals to play an active role in managing their mental health (Kapitan, 2012; Wyller et al, 2017). Moreover, as a result of the pervasive diet culture, many people have a toxic relationship with exercise and body-oriented activities in general and see them as a means of controlling their body's size and shape. However, self-care, not self-control, should be the focus of exercise. For this reason, we prefer the term "movement" for "exercise," as it does not carry the same connotations.

Mind-body Interventions are potentially cost-effective, non-invasive, and straightforward to implement both in clinical practice and home setting (Wahbeh et al., 2008) and as self-care practice. Mind-body interventions (MBIs) including meditation, yoga, somatic education and mindfulness training, have been considered helpful in stress-related diseases by fostering resilience through self-care (Dossett et al., 2020). However, to be regarded as reliable and useful, results must be replicated across a variety of subjects and circumstances (Petticrew & Roberts, 2008).

According to a recent study, people with higher SPS scores may exercise less frequently and, when they do, may prefer to avoid vigorous-intensity activities (Webb, 2022). For people with high SPS, more research is required to identify appropriate Mind-Body Interventions, and to investigate the feasibility of the identified interventions in terms of accessibility, appropriateness, and meaningfulness for people with high SPS.

A thorough, systematic, and transparent review of the literature will be done in order to study the evidence and enhance knowledge of the role that mind-body and movement interventions have in improving well-being for people with high SPS.

Aim

This systematic review, which is based on the FAME (Feasibility, Appropriateness, Meaningfulness, and Effectiveness) framework (Pearson et al., 2015), aims to assess the availability, feasibility, and effectiveness of Mind-body interventions (MBIs), such as meditation, yoga, mindful movement, somatic education, and mindfulness training, in promoting wellbeing for people with high SPS. The objectives are:

- To identify interventions that use mind-body mindful movement, sport, or somatic education somatic education for individuals high in SPS;
- To explore feasibility, in terms of accessibility, appropriateness, and meaningfulness of the identified interventions for individuals high in SPS;
- To determine effectiveness of the identified interventions in improving global well-being and/or aspects of well-being for individual high in SPS.

Methods

The review will be conducted as described in a protocol registered in Zenodo, a multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN compliant with the data management requirements of Horizon Europe, the ERC and other EU research and innovation funding programmes, and it will be reported according to PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The review will be conducted in five stages: literature search, study selection, data extraction, quality assessment, and data analysis.

Design

A mixed-method systematic review methodology will be used to achieve the review's objectives. Using triangulation techniques, mixed-methods research encourages the collection of quantitative and qualitative data, a thorough analysis of the intervention impacts from several perspectives, and the validation of findings (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Hong et al., 2017).

Selection criteria

The SPIO (Study design, Population, Interventions, and Outcomes) framework, targeting the key components of the research study, was used to determine the selection criteria (Table 1).

Table 1 - SPIO inclusion/exclusion criteria

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Study design	Any, except those in exclusion criteria.	Systematic review and literature review
Population	Individuals high in SPS	Presence of neurological diseases
Intervention	Mind-Body Interventions: approaches implementing different types of behavioural exercises to promote the connection between mind and body; any health practice that combines mental focus, controlled breathing, and body movements to help relax the body and mind such as meditation, yoga, mindful movement, somatic education, physical activity and mindfulness training aimed at promoting wellbeing for people with high SPS Any mind-body intervention intended as approach except those in exclusion criteria	Mind-body intervention involving manipulation, mobilisation, body sensors, movement, and posture re-education (e.g., acupuncture, chiropractic, and osteopathic manipulation, biofeedback, etc.)
Outcome	Any outcome related to global well-being and/or aspects of well-being, included executive functioning (e.g., confidence, social participation,	

	attention controls, mood disorders, quality of life, cognition, communication, etc.)	
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SPIO is an adaptation of the Population, Interventions, Comparison, and Outcomes framework (Bettany-Saltikov, 2012).

Population: individuals high in SPS or mixed populations where the individuals high in SPS-only data can be extracted.

Interventions: Mind-Body Interventions. In the context of this review, Mind-Body Interventions can be defined as approaches implementing different types of behavioural exercises to promote the connection between mind and body with the aim of enhancing health and well-being (Love et al., 2019) and as *“a health practice that combines mental focus, controlled breathing, and body movements to help relax the body and mind”* (National Cancer Institute, 2022). Any intervention procedures, duration, and intensity will be included, as far as data about the review-relevant intervention could be extracted.

This review will exclude the following: interventions with review with different primary target outcomes such as interventions including selected elements derived from mind-body and/or mindful movement used to target outcomes that deviate from the primary scope of this review.

Study design: all study designs have been included (quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method).

Outcomes: any outcome measuring global well-being and/or aspects of well-being (e.g., well-being, mood, confidence, social participation, Quality of Life (QoL), communication, cognition, and fatigue).

Search methods

Scoping searches were conducted in a systematic review repository (i.e., *Cochrane*) to identify systematic reviews in the field and in three bibliographic databases to refine the search terms (i.e., Web of Science, Scopus and *MEDLINE*). Search strings will be developed combining subject headings and keywords targeting the Population and Intervention parameters of the SPIO framework through Booleans operators. The pool of keywords will be expanded by identifying concepts and synonyms through a mind map process. A filter (i.e., Title and abstract only) will be applied to the search in databases where an excessive number of irrelevant sources will be retrieved (e.g., Proquest).

No delimiters in time of publication will be applied to the search. Language restriction will be not applied for this search as the main reviewer can understand a good number of languages and has access to speakers of a wide range of languages who could assist with translation.

The finalised search will be run in seven databases, i.e., PubMed – Medline, Scopus, APA PsycInfo, Social Sciences Citation Index, ProQuest, ProQuest all databases, Web of Science.

The authors will be contacted if the full paper could not be fully accessed online and/or when additional information would be necessary to determine eligibility (e.g., extracted data).

Study selection

Titles and abstracts of all identified studies were screened by two reviewers (MF and AB). Studies will be coded as follows: “included”, “excluded”, and “undecided”. Where inclusion will be uncertain, the reviewer will err on the side of inclusion. Full text of “included” and “undecided” papers will be independently reviewed by two of the authors (MF and AF) to identify eligible studies. Any potential disagreement will be resolved through discussion and referral to a third reviewer, when necessary. As part of the selection process, it was decided to exclude unpublished studies, which did not report information systematically.

Data extraction

To ensure rigour and systematicity, data in terms of population, study design and methods, interventions, and outcomes were extracted using a bespoke tool based on the domains of the *Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR)* checklist (Hoffmann et al., 2014). The second reviewer (AB) independently will extract data for at least 50% of the included studies.

Quality appraisal

Standardised design-specific quality appraisal checklists will be used to categorise each study and assess its quality. The following tools will be used: the *Joanna Briggs Institute Critical Appraisal Checklist for Quasi-Experimental Studies, Analytical Cross Sectional Studies, Case Control Studies, Case Reports, Case Series and Cohort Studies, Qualitative Studies* (JBI Checklists, 2020), the *Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Randomised Controlled Trial Checklist* (CASP Checklists, 2020). Single-case studies using qualitative methods will be appraised using the CASP Qualitative Checklist as questions seemed more appropriate than those of the *JBI Case Reports*. The reviewer will classify the studies as follows: “poor” studies with a score <5; “medium” studies with a score between 5 and 8, and “high” studies with scores ≥8. The second reviewer will independently assess the quality of at least 50% of the included studies.

Synthesis of results

Quantitative and qualitative investigations will be analysed in two separate syntheses as part of a segregated synthesis (Sandelowski et al., 2006). We will employ a revised Effect Direction Plot to analyse quantitative studies. With the help of this technique, it is possible to investigate the efficacy of interventions using data on outcome improvement, decrement, or no change. (Thomson & Thomas, 2013; Boon & Thomson, 2021).

In systematic reviews that include non-randomized studies and many sources of data, when meta-analysis cannot be done and effect sizes are not available for all the investigations, it has been demonstrated that Effect Direction Plots are appropriate to synthesise effect measures (Boon & Thomson, 2021). Data will be visually represented in a table.

Qualitative findings from the included studies will be synthesised using thematic synthesis. Specifically, a three-stage process, which may overlap to some degree, will be used to analyse and combine secondary qualitative data: the free line-by-line coding of the findings of primary studies; the organisation of these free codes into related areas to construct descriptive themes; and the development of analytical themes. This approach enables reviewers to preserve the findings from the primary studies and integrate these by transparently generating novel constructs within a specific research context (Thomas & Harden, 2008).

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